

into the half cells. In the drop contact technique developed above, it is evident that the half cells are free from any such deteriorations. The ageing effect with time is also absent. Large quantities of cell liquids, as in the case of flowing junctions, are also unnecessary. The method may also be of great value in the case of *c. m. f.* measurements with colloidal solutions, where the bridge liquid often introduces further complications by coagulation of the colloids at the tips of the connecting tubes.

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A Note on the Reduction of Selenium Dioxide by Carbon Monoxide.

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Carbon monoxide from formate was dried over P_2O_5 and freed from traces of oxygen by passing over red hot copper gauze and then granulated potassium hydroxide. Selenium dioxide was sublimed into the vessels (cleansed by chromic, nitric acid mixture) in a dry stream of oxygen with a little NO_2 (oxygen carrier). Carbon monoxide was then introduced by repeated evacuation. With sealed glass tubes no reduction had taken place after several days' exposure to tropical sunlight. With a quartz vessel no reduction was brought about by several hours' exposure to intense radiation from a quartz mercury lamp. By slowly heating sealed glass tubes in an electrical heater with a mica window slight reduction was observed to occur at about 250° . By careful heating, however, in a quartz vessel it was found that selenium dioxide could be sublimed unchanged in carbon monoxide. By continually subliming a quantity of selenium dioxide from one side of a vessel to the other in a stream of carbon monoxide by strong heating with a bare gas flame only 17.2 mg. of selenium was separated after 40 minutes and only 16 mg. of CO was collected in the absorption tube.

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